

Physical Set-Up and Approximations for Light Curve Modeling

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1 Physical Set-up and Approximations

Computing the pulse profile observed at infinity from a spinning neutron star requires considering a number of different physical processes: the reprocessing of the photons in the neutron-star atmosphere (which determines the spectrum and beaming of the emerging radiation), the shape of the neutron star (which determines the boundary conditions for photon propagation), and the gravitational lensing in its spacetime. In this section, we discuss the approximations for these physical processes that have been employed by the different numerical algorithms.

1.1 The Neutron-Star Spacetime

In principle, the spacetime of a neutron star depends on its mass, spin, and equation of state. However, unless a neutron-star spins nears its breakup limit, a number of useful approximations exist that simplify significantly the calculations.

At the limit of zero spin, the shape of the neutron-star surface is spherical and its external spacetime is described by the Schwarzschild metric. To first order in the spin frequency, the shape of the neutron star remains spherical but the spacetime is that of Kerr. The three additional effects that alter the pulse profiles at infinity are frame dragging, time delays, and the Doppler effects from the spin velocity of the stellar surface. Frame dragging effects are subdominant compared to the latter two (Braje et al. 2000; Psaltis & Özel 2014) and this has led to the Schwarzschild+Doppler (S+D) approximation in which the external spacetime of the neutron star is described by the Schwarzschild metric but the special relativistic effects associated with the stellar rotation are explicitly taken into account (Miller & Lamb 1998; Poutanen & Gierlinski 2003).

To second order in the spin frequency, the neutron star becomes oblate and its spacetime is described by the Hartle-Thorne metric that has a non-zero quadrupole moment. Fitting formulae exist that connect the oblateness and quadrupole moment of the neutron star to its mass, radius, and spin frequency, independent of the equation of state (Morsink et al. 2007; Baubock et al. 2013). Of the two effects, the oblateness is dominant (Morsink et al. 2007; Psaltis & Özel 2014). This has led to the Oblate Schwarzschild (OS) approximation (Morsink et al. 2007), in which the spacetime of the neutron star is described by the Schwarzschild metric, the special relativistic Doppler effects are explicitly taken into account as in the Schwarzschild+Doppler approximation, but the neutron-star surface is assumed to be oblate.

Finally, for even higher spin frequencies, the external spacetime of the neutron star depends on the details of the equation-of-state (see, however, Pappas & Apostolatos 2013 for a general analytic approximation to such a metric). Cadeau et al. (2007) have developed an algorithm that calculates pulse profiles for neutron stars with arbitrary spin frequencies, using numerical spacetimes.

1.1.1 The Schwarzschild+Doppler Approximation

Different numerical algorithms in this code-comparison project use different approximations. We formally derive now the equations of the Schwarzschild+Doppler approximation from the fully general relativistic formalism, in order to demonstrate the equivalence of the two approaches and to resolve a subtle point regarding the definition of the effective area on the neutron-star surface of the emitting region. In the following, we will follow the general approach of Cadeau et al. (2007), Morsink et al. (2007), and Poutanen & Gierlinski (2003). We will denote by M and R the mass and radius of the neutron star and set $G = c = 1$.

We will assume that the exterior spacetime of the neutron star is described by the Schwarzschild

metric. When expressed in Schwarzschild coordinates, it is given by

$$ds^2 = g_{tt}dt^2 + g_{rr}dr^2 + g_{\theta\theta}d\theta^2 + g_{\phi\phi}d\phi^2, \quad (1)$$

with

$$-g_{tt} = \frac{1}{g_{rr}} = 1 - \frac{2M}{r} \quad (2)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} g_{\theta\theta} &= r^2 \\ g_{\phi\phi} &= r^2 \sin^2 \theta. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

This metric has two Killing vectors, which we will denote by $\xi^\mu = (1, 0, 0, 0)$ and $\eta^\nu = (0, 0, 0, 1)$.

The angular spin frequency of the neutron star, as measured by an observer at infinity is Ω . The 4-velocity of a surface element on the neutron star is equal to

$$u_*^\mu = \frac{1}{\sqrt{-g_{tt} - g_{\phi\phi}\Omega^2}} (\xi^\mu + \Omega\eta^\nu) = \frac{1}{1 - \frac{2M}{R} - \Omega^2 R^2 \sin^2 \theta} (1, 0, 0, \Omega), \quad (4)$$

with the various components obtained from the requirements that

$$\frac{d\phi}{dt} = \frac{u_*^\phi}{u_*^t} = \Omega \quad (5)$$

and

$$g_{\mu\nu}u_*^\mu u_*^\nu = -1. \quad (6)$$

For reasons that will become obvious when we consider the S+D approximation, we define the relativistic factors

$$\beta_* \equiv \frac{\Omega R \sin \theta}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2M}{R}}} \quad (7)$$

and

$$\gamma_* \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \beta_*^2}}, \quad (8)$$

so that the 4-velocity of the surface element becomes

$$u_*^\mu = \frac{\gamma_*}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2M}{R}}} (1, 0, 0, \Omega). \quad (9)$$

We will consider photons with angular momenta k^μ traveling from the neutron-star surface to the image plane of an observer at infinity. If we denote by

$$l = g_{\mu\nu}k^\mu \eta^\nu \quad (10)$$

the conserved angular momentum of the photon and by

$$e = -g_{\mu\nu}k^\mu \xi^\nu \quad (11)$$

the conserved energy of the photon, then we can write the impact parameter of its trajectory as

$$b \equiv \frac{l}{e} = \frac{R^2 \sin^2 \theta k^\phi}{(1 - \frac{2M}{R})k^t}. \quad (12)$$

The Energy Change of a Photon.— Our first goal is to calculate the energy change of a photon as it travels from the neutron star surface to the observer at infinity. In the full general relativistic calculation, the ratio of the photon energy at infinity E_∞ to that on the stellar surface E_* is calculated using the time Killing symmetry of the spacetime as

$$\frac{E_\infty}{E_*} \Big|_{\text{GR}} = \frac{-g_{\mu\nu,\infty} k_\infty^\mu u_0^\nu}{-g_{\mu\nu,*} k_*^\mu u_*^\nu} \quad (13)$$

where $u_0^\mu = \xi^\mu$ is the 4-velocity of the observer at infinity. This quantity is denoted by $1 + z$ in equation (16) of Cadeau et al. (2007) and by ϵ in equation (6) of Psaltis & Özel (2014; see also eq. [24] of Psaltis & Johannsen 2012). Plugging equations (9), (11), and (12) into equation (13) we obtain

$$\frac{E_\infty}{E_*} \Big|_{\text{GR}} = \frac{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2M}{R}}}{\gamma_*(1 - \Omega b)} \quad (14)$$

In the S+D approximation, the change in the photon energy is calculated in two steps: first, the photon energy is Doppler shifted from a frame comoving with the surface element to that of a standing observer at the same place in the spacetime; second, the photon energy is gravitationally redshifted from the neutron-star surface to the observer at infinity.

In order to perform the first Doppler shift using Special Relativity, we need to calculate the 3-velocity of a surface element on the neutron star, as measured by a static observer there. The static observer on the neutron star has a 4-velocity

$$u_{\text{obs}}^\mu = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2M}{R}}} (1, 0, 0, 0) \quad (15)$$

and we can use this to define the spatial projection operator for this observer as

$$h^{\mu\nu} = g^{\mu\nu} + u_{\text{obs}}^\mu u_{\text{obs}}^\nu. \quad (16)$$

The magnitude of the 3-velocity of the surface element as measured by the static observer is given by the projection of its 4-velocity (eq.[9]) using this operator, divided by the locally measured Lorentz factor, i.e.,

$$v_* = \frac{(h_{\mu\nu} u_*^\mu u_*^\nu)^{1/2}}{|g_{\mu\nu} u_{\text{obs}}^\mu u_*^\nu|}, \quad (17)$$

with the denominator (i.e., the locally measured Lorentz factor) being equal to the projection of the 4-velocity of the surface element to the 4-velocity of the static observer. Using equations (9) and (15), we obtain

$$|g_{\mu\nu} u_{\text{obs}}^\mu u_*^\nu| = |g_{tt} u_{\text{obs}}^t u_*^t| = \gamma_* \quad (18)$$

and

$$v_* = \frac{\Omega R \sin \theta}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2M}{R}}} = \beta_*. \quad (19)$$

These equations justify our definitions of β_* and γ_* : they represent the magnitude of the 3-velocity and the corresponding Lorentz factor of the surface element, as measured by a static observer in the same place in the spacetime.

In order to calculate the Doppler shift of the photon energy, we also need to calculate the angle ξ_v between the 3-velocity of the surface element and the direction of propagation of the photon, both measured by the local static observer. Using the same projection operator, we have

$$\cos \xi_v = \frac{h_{\mu\nu} u_*^\mu k^\nu}{(h_{\mu\nu} u_*^\mu u_*^\nu) (h_{\mu\nu} k_*^\mu k_*^\nu)}. \quad (20)$$

Making use of the previous definitions, of the impact parameter b (eq. [12]), and of the null conditions for the photons, i.e., $g_{\mu\nu} k^\mu k^\nu = 0$, we obtain

$$\cos \xi_v = \frac{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2M}{R}}}{R \sin \theta} b. \quad (21)$$

Using equations (19) and (21), we can now calculate the Doppler factor as

$$\delta \equiv \frac{1}{\gamma_*(1 - \beta \cos \xi_v)} = \frac{1}{\gamma_*(1 - \Omega b)}. \quad (22)$$

This is the Doppler factor δ in equation (10) of Poutanen & Gierlinski (2003) and the Doppler factor η in equation (33) of Morsink et al. (2007).

Finally, applying the gravitational redshift that the photon experiences when traveling from the neutron-star surface to the observer at infinity, we obtain the total energy shift in the S+D approximation as

$$\left. \frac{E_\infty}{E_*} \right|_{\text{S+D}} = \frac{\sqrt{1 - \frac{2M}{R}}}{\gamma_*(1 - \Omega b)}. \quad (23)$$

This equation is identical to eq. (14) (as it should) that was derived in a different manner.

The Observed Flux.— The flux observed by a distant observer at a given photon energy E_∞ and at a given time t is given by the integral of the specific intensity over the solid angle on the image plane, i.e.,

$$F(E_\infty, t) = \int I_\infty(E_\infty, t) d\Omega. \quad (24)$$

In the full general relativistic calculation, when the spacetime is not spherically symmetric due to frame dragging and the quadrupole moment, this integral is calculated on a Cartesian frame on the image plane as

$$F(E_\infty, t) = \int \int I_\infty(\alpha_0, \beta_0, E_\infty, t) \frac{d\alpha_0 d\beta_0}{D^2}; \quad (25)$$

Here α_0 and β_0 are two Cartesian coordinates on the image plane and D is the distance from the center of the neutron star to the observer.

Ray tracing connects via null geodesics each location (α_0, β_0) on the image plane to a point on the neutron star surface with longitude $\phi(\alpha_0, \beta_0)$ and latitude $\theta(\alpha_0, \beta_0)$. When it hits the stellar surface, the null geodesic makes an angle $\alpha(\alpha_0, \beta_0)$ with respect to the normal to the stellar surface and has traveled for a coordinate time $t_d(\alpha_0, \beta_0)$ between the star and the observer. With these definitions and making use of the Lorentz invariance of the photon occupation number along a null geodesic, we can write the observed flux as

$$F(E_\infty, t) = \int \int \left(\frac{E_\infty}{E_*} \right)^3 I_{NS}[\phi(\alpha_0, \beta_0), \theta(\alpha_0, \beta_0), \alpha(\alpha_0, \beta_0), E_{NS}, t - t_d(\alpha_0, \beta_0)] \frac{d\alpha_0 d\beta_0}{D^2}. \quad (26)$$

This is equation (1) of Psaltis & Özel (2014), with the beaming angle α denoted there as δ .

The quantity $I_{\text{NS}}(\phi, \theta, \delta, E_{\text{NS}}, t)$ is the specific intensity of photons with energy E_{NS} that emerges at coordinate time t from a location on the neutron star surface with latitude ϕ , longitude θ and at an angle α with respect to the local normal. Note that, because of the differential light travel time t_d , photons that arrive at the same time on the image plane may have left the neutron-star surface at different times. The specific intensity on the neutron-star surface is assumed to be given by separate calculations and is simply prescribed for ray tracing.

For the simple problems employed in this code-comparison project, the neutron-star is assumed to be emitting uniformly within a circular hot spot of angular radius ρ and with a center at a colatitude θ_s . *For reasons that will become important below, we emphasize that the size of the spot is defined here using the locus of points on the stellar surface for which local observers (eq. [15]) with synchronized clocks see emission emerging from the surface simultaneously.*

In the Schwarzschild+Doppler approximation, the spherical symmetry of the spacetime allows transforming the integral over the solid angle on the image plane into one over the emitting surface area on the neutron star. It is straightforward to show that the differential solid angle in equation (26) is (see eq. [7] of Poutanen & Gierlinski 2003)

$$d\Omega \equiv \frac{d\alpha_0 d\beta_0}{D^2} = \frac{dS \cos \alpha}{D^2} \frac{1}{1 - \frac{2M}{R}} \frac{d \cos \alpha}{d \cos \psi}, \quad (27)$$

where ψ is the lensing angle given by equation (3) in Poutanen & Gierlinski (2003). The surface area dS is *not* the locus of points on the neutron-star surface that emit simultaneously. Instead, it is the locus of points on the neutron star surface that correspond to emission of photons that arrive simultaneously on the image plane of the observer. Because of the differential light travel times and the rotation of the neutron star, we get (see equations [31]-[33] in Morsink et al. 2007¹)

$$dS = \frac{dS'}{1 - \Omega b} = \gamma_* \delta dS' \quad (28)$$

where dS' is surface area of the locus of points on the surface that emit simultaneously and we have used equation (22) for the Doppler factor δ .

Plugging equations (23), (22), (27), and (28) into equation (26), we obtain

$$dF(E_\infty, t) = \gamma_* \delta^4 \left(1 - \frac{2M}{R}\right)^{1/2} I_{\text{NS}}(\phi, \theta, \alpha, E_{\text{NS}}) \frac{dS' \cos \alpha}{D^2} \frac{d \cos \alpha}{d \cos \psi}, \quad (29)$$

Comparing this result to equation (13) of Poutanen & Gierlinski (2003; after plugging in their eq. [6]) and to equation (14) of Lo et al. (2013; after plugging in their eqs.[5]-[10]), we see that the two expressions differ by a factor γ_* .

The missing γ_* factor in the Poutanen & Gierlinski (2003) expression arises from a difference in the definition of the observers that measure the differential surface area dS' . In the fully general relativistic approach, dS' is defined based on the simultaneous measurements of local static observers (with their 4-velocities given by eq. [15]). In the S+D approach of Poutanen & Gierlinski (2003), dS' is defined based on the simultaneous measurements of observers that are comoving locally with each surface element (with their 4-velocities given by eq. [9]). A measurement that is simultaneous

¹Note that going from their eq. (33) to eq. (41), Morsink et al. (2007) introduced an additional factor γ perhaps to simplify the notation, only because they are strictly working in the S+D approximation, i.e., to first order in the surface velocity of the star, for which $\gamma = 1$. Had they not neglected second-order terms in the surface velocity, an additional factor γ would have appeared in their eq. (41).

for the static observers is not for the comoving observers and taking this non-simultaneity into account leads to the additional factor γ_* (see Ghisellini 1999).

It might appear that the choice of observers is arbitrary and, therefore, that both approaches are equally appropriate. This is true for large surface elements in a linear motion or for infinitesimally small surface elements in an arbitrary motion. It is not true, however, for an extended hot spot on a spinning neutron star, which is the case we are considering here. To see the problem, we will consider the extreme case of an infinitesimally thin “hot spot” on the stellar equator that extends all around the star; in other words, we will consider a “hot spot” that traces the stellar diameter on the equator. We will then consider small segments on this spot and assign two observers comoving with the trailing and the leading edge of the segment. As measured by the static observers, the clock of the leading comoving observer for segment one will always lead the clock of the trailing observer for the same segment. Moving on to the successive segments, we will build up a significant lag between the leading observer of the n -th segment and the trailing observer of the 1st segment. By the time we make a full circle, the leading observer of the last segment will be colocated with the trailing observer of the 1st segment, both observers will be moving with the same velocity, but their two clocks (as measured by static observers) will not be synchronized. This is clearly not an appropriate set of observers that we can use to define the surface area of the emitting region on the neutron-star surface.

Even for a moderately spinning neutron star with a spin frequency of 200 Hz, the magnitude of the Lorentz γ_* at the equator is (assuming $M = 1.4M_\odot$ and $R = 12$ km)

$$\gamma_* = \left[1 - \frac{\Omega^2 R^2}{1 - \frac{2M}{R}} \right]^{-1/2} \simeq 1 + 1.9 \times 10^{-3} \left(\frac{\Omega/2\pi}{200 \text{ Hz}} \right)^2 \left(\frac{R}{12 \text{ km}} \right)^2 \quad (30)$$

i.e., it differs from unity by an amount that is larger than our target accuracy of 10^{-3} . If we were to be strict in our application of the Schwarzschild+Doppler approximation, we would have to set $\gamma_* = 1$ and drop all such terms. In fact, it is not self-consistent to keep Lorentz γ_* terms and drop other effects that are second order in the spin of the neutron star, such as the oblate shape of the surface and the quadrupole moment. However, if we are going to keep the Lorentz γ_* terms (as we will in the Schwarzschild+Oblate approximation) then we need to do it in a consistent way.

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